

Shakti Act : A Beacon of Hope for Maharashtra's Women

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Abstract : *The efficacy of Maharashtra, India's Shakti Act of 2020, a legislative measure aimed at reducing violence against women and children, depends on public knowledge. The purpose of this study is to find out how much the people of Maharashtra currently know about the provisions of the Act. The study uses focused approaches, such as surveys and questionnaires, in addition to media depictions. It seeks to determine the degree of comprehension among various demographic groups, paying special attention to those who might be at risk. Any disparities in awareness depending on social background, location, or information access will be clarified by this investigation. This research can help shape targeted outreach programs and educational initiatives by detecting awareness gaps. For the Act's intended beneficiaries to be able to take advantage of the legal protections it provides, there has to be a greater awareness among the public of its provisions. By reducing ignorance about the Shakti Act, this study seeks to make Maharashtra a safer place for women to live.*

Keywords : Shakti Act, Awareness, Women, Maharashtra.

Introduction

Rape is an abhorrent aspect of human existence; both men and women who are victims of it suffer greatly locally. Several Indian states have taken extremely serious measures against this horrible deed. As an illustration, consider the Andhra Pradesh and Disha Act 2019, which has been proposed in numerous states and established a standard for aiding female victims. Anil Deshmukh, the home minister, introduced the Shakti Bill in the Legislative Assembly in order to address this. The prevention of violence against women and children will be

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aided by this law. This law stipulates that the prosecution of the accused must be finished in 21 days.

Within fifteen days, the police had to wrap up their investigation. The Andhra Pradesh Disha Act is being considered as this Act is being written. Globally, violence against women is still widespread and severe, with a high proportion of documented cases occurring in India. As a result, the Indian government passed number of laws to defend women's rights and stop gender-based violence. Among these, the state of Maharashtra's Shakti Act (Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005) and Disha Act (The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013) from Andhra Pradesh are prominent.

Shakti Act :

In the Indian state of Maharashtra, the Shakti Act, 2020 is a comprehensive law designed to improve the protection and security of women. In response to the mounting worries about sexual harassment, violence against women, and other related offenses, it was put into law. Maharashtra's Shakti Act is a big step in the right direction for women's protection and welfare. The goal of the Act is to make women feel safer and discourage future perpetrators by offering harsher punishments, quicker trials, and support programs.

Enacted in 2005, the Shakti Act is a landmark legislation that provides a comprehensive legal framework for protecting women from domestic violence. It recognizes domestic violence as a cognizable and non-bailable offense, empowering women to seek legal remedies and obtain various forms of protection, including residence orders, custody orders, and monetary relief.

Maharashtra Police have proposed amendments to the Shakti Act, 2020, aiming to further strengthen the Act's provisions and deter heinous crimes against women and children.

Key Amendments

- **Expanding the scope of offenses :** The amendments propose to include new offenses under the Act, such as stalking, voyeurism, and sharing of obscene content online.
- **Provision for special courts :** The amendments call for the establishment of special courts to expedite trials and ensure speedy justice for victims.

- **Increased penalties :** Under the Act, criminals found guilty of crimes against women, including as rape, domestic abuse, and sexual harassment, will face tougher sentences.
- **Fast Trials :** In order to ensure prompt justice, it requires the creation of special fast-track courts to expedite the trial of cases pertaining to crimes against women.
- **Protection Orders :** The Act gives women the legal right to seek protection orders from those who harass or abuse them, giving them a way to defend themselves.
- **Victim Compensation :** It helps victims of crimes against women heal from the pain and potential financial losses they may have experienced by providing compensation.
- **Efforts to Raise Awareness :** The Act places a strong emphasis on the need to use public education initiatives and campaigns to raise awareness of women's rights and safety.

Significance of the Amendments

In Maharashtra, India, the Shakti Act is crucial for protecting women's safety and welfare. The following are some of its main implications:

1. **Crime deterrence :** The severe penalties imposed by the Act for crimes against women work as a forceful deterrence, turning away potential perpetrators and making it abundantly evident that such behavior will not be accepted.
2. **Justice for victims :** The Act gives victims of crimes against women a legal framework within which to pursue redress and receive compensation, assisting in their recovery from any trauma and possible monetary losses.
3. **Women's protection :** The Act gives women the authority to use protection orders and other tools to defend themselves against abuse and harassment, giving them a sense of security and self-assurance.
4. **Advancement of women's rights :** The Act reaffirms the significance of equality and women's rights, making it clear that women should be able to live without fear of discrimination or oppression.

5. **Better law enforcement :** The Act's provisions for extra awareness campaigns and special fast-track courts have enhanced law enforcement procedures and brought more attention to crimes against women.
6. **Changes in society :** The Act has aided in a wider cultural movement that has promoted a more inclusive and equitable society by raising awareness of and understanding for women's issues.

Overall, the Shakti Act is a significant piece of legislation that has had a positive impact on the lives of women in Maharashtra. By providing stronger legal protections, deterring crime, and promoting women's rights, the Act has helped to create a safer and more just environment for women.

Concerns and Considerations

Although it is admirable that the Act's efficacy is being increased, worries about potential abuse and the appropriateness of punishments should be carefully taken into account during the legislative process. In general, the suggested modifications signify a noteworthy advancement in fortifying the legislative structure to counteract offenses against females and minors in Maharashtra. But maintaining a fair and human rights-based strategy is still essential.

Problem of the study and Research questions :

- Has the Act effectively reduced violence against women in Maharashtra?
- Has the Shakti Act affected perceptions of women's safety in Maharashtra?
- Has the Shakti Act had any significant impact on the incidence of crimes against women in Maharashtra?

Modifications made by state governments that the federal government has not yet adopted. However, the act's flaw is the states' women's extremely low level of awareness. Therefore, the research paper's main focus is on raising awareness among state women. It will assist in lowering Maharashtra's crime rate.

Review of Literature

Pam Rajput, Usha Thakkar (2023) : The writers talked about the Maharashtra Shakti Criminal Law, the (Maharashtra Amendment) Act 2020, the Special Court, and the Mechanism for implementing the Maharashtra Shakti Criminal Law, 2020 in order to lessen crimes against women and children. The death sentence is one of the legal punishments for serious crimes like rape.

Sadaf Modak (Dec; 2021) : It has been focused on the Shakti Criminal Laws (Maharashtra Amendment) Act, which was passed by the Maharashtra Assembly on Thursday, December 23, with unanimous votes. Once the Bill was approved, it became the second state in India, after Andhra Pradesh, to adopt the death penalty for heinous rape and gang rape offenses. The relevant parts of the Criminal Procedure Code and the Acts protecting children from sexual offenses (POCSO) and the Indian Penal Code against rape, gangrape, acid attacks, and sexual harassment have been changed by the Assembly.

Rajendra Prasad (2022) : According to Rajendra Prasad's article in his current affairs yearbook 2022, the Maharashtra Assembly unanimously enacted the Shakti Criminal Laws (Maharashtra Amendment) Act. Context After Andhra Pradesh gave its consent, Maharashtra was proclaimed the second state in India.

Research Gap : There are many articles available in newspapers and some descriptions in books on various current affairs. So far, there is no reference to the scrutiny of this Act. Therefore, this is an honest attempt of the researcher to know the public awareness of this law in Maharashtra itself and its effect on women's crimes in the future.

Objectives

1. To determine the historical context of the Maharashtra State Shakti Act
2. To examine awareness of the Shakti Act concerning incidents of violence against women in Maharashtra.
3. To assess the Shakti Act's effects on various involved people
4. To make recommendations for enhancing the Act's efficacy

With these few objectives, the following hypothesis is formulated to explore the awareness of Shakti Act in the State of Maharashtra.

Hypothesis

H_0 : The Shakti Act has not had a significant impact on the incidence of crimes against women in Maharashtra.

H_1 : The Shakti Act has had a significant impact on the incidence of crimes against women in Maharashtra.

Research Methodology

Data Collection : Primary data was collected through questionnaire. Secondary data was collected through various current affairs books, articles in the newspapers, blogs and e-sources.

Sample size : 117 samples have been collected through simple random sampling method

Statistical tools : Mann-Whitney U Test used for justification of hypothesis.

Limitations of the study : The number of responses was small; the responses are taken only from Mumbai division and these responses are influenced by newspaper articles or hearsay incidents.

Justification of Hypothesis

H_0 : The Shakti Act has not had a significant impact on the incidence of crimes against women in Maharashtra.

H_1 : The Shakti Act has had a significant impact on the incidence of crimes against women in Maharashtra.

To evaluate the difference in incidence of crimes with the increase in implementation of the Shakti Act, Mann-Whitney U Test was utilized. This test points towards the impact that Shakti Act has had on incidence of crimes against women in Maharashtra.

Table No. 1 : Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Implementation of Shakti Act	109	2.04	.732	1	4
Incidence of Crimes	109	1.93	.754	1	3

Table No. 2 : Descriptive Statistics - Ranks

	Incidence of Crimes	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Implementation of Shakti Act	Decreased	35	27.51	963.00
	Increased	27	36.67	990.00
	Total	62		

Table No. 3 : Results of Mann Whitney U test – Test Statistics^a

	Implementation of Shakti Act
Mann-Whitney U	333.000
Wilcoxon W	963.000
Z	-2.283
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.022

Grouping Variable: Incidence of Crimes

We shall reject the null hypothesis based on the aforementioned results, where the Z-value is -2.283 and the p-value is 0.022, both of which are less than 0.05. The incidence of crimes varies significantly with the growth of the Shakti Act's implementation. Given that the significant value is 0.022, it may be inferred that, notwithstanding the implementation of the Shakti Act, there is a slight effect on the variance in the occurrence of crimes. It follows that the Shakti Act has significantly reduced the number of crimes against women that occur in Maharashtra.

Other Findings of the Study

Figure-2 : Gender Classification

Of the respondents in the research study, 29% were men and 71% were women. Thus, the proper sex ratio was used for this research.

2) Are you aware about Shakti Act 2020

Figure-3 : Awareness of Shakti Bill

According to Figure 3.61% of respondents are aware of this law, whereas 39% are not.

3) If yes, how familiar are you with the provisions of the Shakti Act?

Figure-4 :

Of those surveyed, 36% claimed to be ignorant of this law. Nonetheless, 53% of those surveyed claimed to only have a passing familiarity with the act—that is, to have heard about it but not in considerable detail.

4) Do you believe that more public awareness of the Shakti Act would deter potential abuse of women?

Figure-5 :

Figure 5, which displays 54% of respondents who agree and 25% who strongly agree, illustrates how awareness discourages violence against women. This indicates that the Maharashtra people has to be made aware of the Shakti Act.

5) Do you think that if more people knew about the Shakti Act, it would give women more confidence to report violent crimes?

Figure-6 :

Figure 6 depicts women’s empowerment and awareness. Of the respondents, 47% agreed and 40% strongly agreed with women’s empowerment. This implies that women’s empowerment may result from knowledge of the Shakti Act.

6) In your opinion, what are the most effective ways to increase awareness of the Shakti Act in Maharashtra?

Figure-7 : Effective ways to Awareness

The pathways of consciousness growth are depicted (in Figure 7). 5% of respondents were in favor of training for law enforcement and judicial officials. While 43% of respondents supported educational programs at schools and colleges, an additional 5% supported community outreach initiatives and 47% concurred with public awareness initiatives.

7) In your opinion, has the incidence of crimes against women in Maharashtra increased, decreased, or remained the same since the implementation of the Shakti Act?

Figure-8 :

People are not very aware of the facts, which has resulted in diverse opinions to the survey mentioned above. Of those surveyed, 24% predicted an increase. Of

those who responded, 33% predicted a drop in crime and 43% said it would stay the same. In their view, there is therefore a great deal of confusion.

8) If increased, what are the reasons?

Figure-9 : If Increased, what are the Reasons ?

The several causes of the rise in crimes against women following the Shakti Act's introduction are depicted in Figure 9. According to 40% of the respondents, it is because they are unaware of this Act. 30% concurred since there was insufficient punishment. While 11% and 17%, respectively, agreed that there was a lack of education and a delayed procedure. Remarkably, just 2 percent attributed crime against women to digital media.

9) If decreased, what are the reasons?

Figure-10 : If Decreased, what are the Reasons ?

Figure 10 focuses on the various reasons for the decline in crimes against women after the implementation of the Shakti Act. 35% of respondents say more awareness is needed. 23% and 21% agree for fear of punishment and more education respectively. While 10% and 11% people agree to promote death penalty and promotion of Act by police respectively.

10) Do you feel safer as a woman in Maharashtra since the implementation of the Shakti Act?

Figure-11 : If Decreased, what are the Reasons ?

Figure 11 shows the safety of women since the introduction of the Shakti Act. 53% and 23% of respondents agreed that women are somewhat safe and significantly safe respectively. 22% respondents agreed about no change in security. But 2% respondents said women are also somewhat less safe.

11) Do you believe the Shakti Act has been effective in deterring crimes against women in Maharashtra?

Figure-12 :

Figure 12 highlights the effectiveness of the Shakti Act against women crime in Maharashtra. 16% and 50% respondents strongly agree and somewhat agree respectively. 31% are neutral.

12) Recommendations for strengthening of Act

Figure-13 :

From all the above research some recommendations are given by the respondents like about 62% of the respondents suggested speedy court for punishment of criminals. 78% suggested more awareness. 57% of the respondents suggested that schools and colleges should emphasize Shakti Act knowledge. 41% of the respondents suggested that police should conduct seminars and workshops related to Shakti Act and create public awareness. 36% suggested that it should be approved by the central government quickly. 31% also suggested that politicians should speak at each of their public meetings.

Conclusion

In order to lessen horrible crimes against women in Maharashtra, the Shakti Act is crucial. Yet, greater awareness is required, raising red flags for criminals. Hence the alternate hypothesis in the research opposing theory that “the Shakti Act has had a significant impact on the incidence of crimes against women in Maharashtra” is accepted. The difference in crime rates with increases in law enforcement authority was assessed using the Mann-Whitney U test. This test shows how the Shakti Act has affected the number of crimes against women in Maharashtra.

The current status of decline in incidents among Maharashtrians in relation to the Shakti Act's provisions has been brought to light by this research. It will be advantageous for victims' rights advocacy and women's safety. This will give Maharashtrian women more influence. This is the researcher's ultimate objective.

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